

Motives of Social Behavior and Personal Motivation

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Abstract: In this article, another common way of classifying activities and dividing them into types is to classify them according to the main types of activity characteristic of all people, and motivation is to clarify the psychological reasons that explain human behavior, its connection, direction and activity, and the means of achieving the goal. It is implied that the means should justify the achievement of the goal.

Keywords: need, program, purposeful action, norms of social behavior, types of activity, social institution, social objects of a person, cognitive component, affective component, types of need, biological need.

Society is a set of social relations formed at a certain stage of human historical development. A person is a part of society. He cannot be out of society. The reasons for this are: firstly, personal morality is always subject to society's morality, it is forced to do so. Secondly, a person can live without many things, but he cannot live in solitude, he finds happiness among people, individual happiness does not exist outside of society; thirdly, one receives encouragement from the will of society; fourthly, the society cares for the development of the individual and provides conditions, a person acquires not only the innate qualities, but also the characteristics specific to this society.

All laws and mechanisms of activity apply to mastering any profession, not just mastering it, but skillfully performing it. It should not be forgotten that in order to simply acquire a professional qualification, it is not just memorizing the information related to it and performing it by recalling it when necessary, but also complex processes related to the conscious performance of both internal (psychic) and external (subject-oriented) actions. But the psychological factors and reasons that force each person to engage in one or another type of activity are important, and are the motives of this activity.

Motives of social behavior and personal motivation. The types of activities that we got acquainted with above do not happen by themselves. The social behavior and behavior of a person in society, the position he occupies, does not happen without a reason. The concepts of "motive" and "motivation" are used in psychology to explain the implementation of activity and the behavior of a person.

The concept of "motivation" has a wider meaning and content than the concept of "motive". Motivation is a set of psychological reasons that explain human behavior, its connection, direction and activity. This concept is used when it is necessary to explain the behavior of one or another person, that is: "why?", "for what?", "for what purpose?", "for what benefit?" Searching for answers to questions means searching for motivation. Therefore, it leads to the clarification of the motivational classification of behavior.

Studying the reasons for a person's behavior and behavior among people in society is something of educational importance, and two aspects of explaining the issue are distinguished: a) internal reasons, that is, the subjective psychological characteristics of the owner of the behavior are meant (motives, needs, goals, goals, desires, interests) etc.); b) external causes - external conditions and circumstances of activity. That is, these are external stimuli that cause the emergence of specific situations.

Control of personal behavior from the inside, due to internal psychological reasons, is usually also called personal dispositions. They may or may not be realized by the individual. That is, sometimes it happens that a person himself does not understand the real reason for the attitude he has formed in relation to the work he has done or changes in himself, "Why?" "I didn't know either, I don't know," he answered. These are called unconscious dispositions or dispositions. If a person is consciously interested in a profession and tries hard to master all its secrets, then the situation is different, that is, the disposition is conscious, conscious.//

From this point of view, the motive is a more concrete concept, which refers to the reason that explains the tendency and presence of a person towards this or that behavior. The famous German scientist Kurt Lewin conducted extensive research on the problem of motives, especially the motives of social behavior in a person, and found out that each person tends to perceive and evaluate this or that situation in his own way. It is surprising that different people's assessments of the same concrete situation are also different. In addition, the same person tends to perceive the same situation in different ways depending on his mood. Therefore, it is more correct to explain the real actions of a person at the moment not as his assessment or reaction to internal and external stimuli in that particular situation, but with the presence of an internal presence - disposition to perceive similar situations.

In this sense, the motivation of a person's behavior includes a complex of reasons based on the experience gained from various conditions, conscious analysis, and even social experience norms. For example, let's say there is a course called "Resistance of Materials" in technical universities. Mastering this course and passing the test is not easy for many people. even before the course begins, young students form such an opinion about this course and its requirements that, of course, this course is difficult, the teacher who conducts it is very demanding, strict, etc. This kind of motivation has been experienced by several generations of students. Now, the next actions of a specific person after the beginning of the lesson process are explained by concrete motives, and for a diligent student, this subject, like other subjects, requires constant research, preparing lessons on time, while for another (for a lazier student), there are no lessons after this lesson and he knows when this semester will end. tries to wait.

Behind any motives lies the needs of the individual. That is, in a purposeful life, one or another needs first appear in a person, and behavioral motives are manifested in a way that depends on their nature and necessity. For example, you can take the student's academic activity. The goal of acquiring knowledge creates a need for knowledge, learning, and curiosity. This need begins to be satisfied at a certain period of development, for example, from the age of kindergarten. The books, notebooks and other educational materials bought for the child, the conditions established in a certain educational place, and the activity aimed at direct learning there, replaces the motive for the child. Another simple example: you have a book in your hand. You haven't started reading it yet. But there is a desire to read, and behind this desire is the need to know the content and understand it. Russian scientist R. Nemov imagines the motivational sphere in a person as follows. In general, the existing needs of any person can be divided into two groups:

Biological needs are physiological (thirst, hunger, sleep), sexual, adaptive needs.

Social needs are labor, knowledge, aesthetic and moral-spiritual needs.

When we divide needs into biological and social types, we must not forget that any needs of an individual are socialized, that is, they depend on the values, cultural norms and character of interpersonal relations in that society and environment. For example, if we take our need for sucking - food, which is considered the most natural and understandable, it also causes different actions depending on the specific environment. For example, at wedding ceremonies or at a very full table, a person does not know why he has eaten so much food. If it's nature's sheep or a weed in a cotton field, even a piece of warm bread is a salve that gives pleasure to the whole body and keeps hunger at bay. A person who has learned to eat food from a modest table gets used to eating little, and a person who has learned to eat more than the norm from a young age goes to the doctor and asks for slimming medicine, but does not know that he should control his intake at home. So, this is directly related to culture, ethics, family environment.

In general, when it comes to the motive of a person's social behavior, two sides or elements of it are distinguished: the program of action and the goal. An action plan specifies the means by which you will achieve your goals. Therefore, the means provided in the program must justify the achievement of the goal, otherwise the program will not give anything. For example, some parents, wishing to raise their children well and grow into the person of their ideals, put very difficult educational conditions in front of them, the child's freedom is stifled, he is caught in an environment of strict control. As a result, the child later becomes uncontrollable, stubborn, less susceptible to external influences, and becomes difficult in any other social situation. That's why the motive should always be understood, the desires coordinated, and the goals and the means to achieve them should be clear. Only then will social behavior be appropriate for society.

Types of motifs. The problem of knowing the nature of motives and changing them is important in studying the motivations of various professions. One such motive is the motive to achieve success in various fields of activity, the founders of this theory are American scientists D. McClelland, D. Atkinson and the German scientist H. Heckhausens are considered. According to them, there are basically two types of motivation that make people do different things: the motivation to succeed and the motivation to avoid failure. People also differ in their motivations for engaging in various activities. For example, people who work only with the motive of success start work with such confidence that achieving success at all costs is their highest goal. They expect success before they even begin, and when they do, they know that people will approve of their every move. In this way, they use not only their own strength and capabilities, but also all external opportunities - familiarity - knowledge, money.

A different behavior can be observed in individuals who rely on the motivation to avoid failure. For example, they, unlike the first, think about not having to face any inconsistency before starting work. Because of this, they have more distrust, lack of belief in achieving success, and a state similar to pessimism. That's probably why, in the end, they still fail and come to the conclusion that "I am a person who does not have good luck". If the people of the first category, after successfully completing one task, start the second task with a high spirit, then the representatives of the second category, after completing any task, regardless of its result, become depressed and start another task with a feeling of pain. Demanding quality plays a big role here. If success-oriented individuals have high demands on themselves, then the demands of the second category are low. In addition, our perception of our real abilities in each of us also affects the place of these motives in the activity. For example, a person who believes in his abilities, even if he loses, does not worry too much, he believes that next time everything will be better. An insecure person experiences even the slightest reprimand or criticism with great emotional pain. For him, the quality of a

person's concern in certain situations determines the nature of motives in a certain sense.

Thus, the system of motives directly results from a person's relationship to work, people, and himself, and also determines his character traits. We can evaluate their manifestation in real conditions in each of us by how we behave and achieve success before any responsible work. Take, for example, the responsible examination process. Some students are very anxious, even afraid, before the exam. Exams are a big worry for them. Others go through this process calmly and, although they are excited from the inside, they do not express it to others. The third category of people are completely innocent and don't care. Naturally, accordingly, the success of the work of representatives of each category and the effectiveness of the activity will be different. It is also affected by the level of assertiveness in each person. If those with a higher level of pretentiousness try to prove what they know and don't know, those with a lower level cannot tell what they know well, and they don't argue with the teacher again.

The degree of awareness of motives: a social institution and the problem of its change. As we noted above, motives, that is, the reasons for our actions, may or may not be understood by us. In all the examples and situations given above, the motive is clear, that is, the person knows why he is doing this or that activity, why he succeeds or fails. But the reasons for our social behavior are not always clear to us. Unrealized motives of social behavior are explained in psychology through the phenomenon of social ustanovka (English "attitude").

Social institution is such a state of readiness of a person to perceive, evaluate and accept social objects, phenomena, groups and individuals, that he does not know exactly when this assessment or attitude was actually formed. For example, we all love our Motherland, our flag is sacred, we believe in German investors, we feel sorry for Negroes, we consider those who are engaged in commercial work to be rich, wealthy, and so on. Without paying attention to when and how these ideas, values and feelings are established in our minds, we continue to experience the emotions listed above. All these are social institutions, the essence of which is actually formed during the social experience of each person and is preserved in long-term memory and is realized in concrete situations.

American scientist G. Allport developed a three-component system of social institution: A. Social institution of a person's social objects Cognitive component - a set of knowledge, ideas, concepts and imaginations related to the institution object;

B. Affective component - real feelings (emotional attitudes such as sympathy, antipathy, indifference) felt by the subject in relation to the object of the superposition; V. action component - a set of actions that the subject can perform in relation to the object in real conditions (manifestation in behavior).

These three components are interrelated, and depending on the situation, the role of one or another component may be more important. It should be said that there may be no similarity between components. For example, although some students are very familiar with student duty and order - discipline, they do not always follow it. Situations such as "accidentally skipping class", "disrupting the order in public places" indicate a lack of harmony in the cognitive and behavioral components. At first glance, this reminds us that the principle of unity of word and work is manifested differently in different individuals. If a person knowingly acts contrary to social behavior several times, and this thing is repeated several times, he gets used to this situation and can become a habit. That's why we need to teach the youth that there should be no such opposition and differences through social norms and sanctions. This has a direct impact on the individual's perspective and performance.

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